

FIBRE OPTIC-BASED PATCH SENSOR FOR THE MONITORING OF REINFORCED CONCRETE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

The past three decades have witnessed remarkable advancements in structural health monitoring (SHM) systems, driven by the need to mitigate accidents involving civil engineering structures. By implementing a proactive maintenance strategy, construction industry professionals can reduce the risk of costly repairs, extend the life of structures, improve safety standards and maximize return on investment. In this context, Leon Grosse alongside Inouid, Brochier Technologies, and the laboratory LOCIE from Université Savoie Mont Blanc are combining their expertise in civil engineering structures construction, sensor development, optical fibers development, and structural diagnostics in buildings within the SENTMI Region project (PSPC Region 2020) to work on the development of an innovative optical fiber based technology. A 2D patch carrying woven optical fibers is tested on concrete structures at different scales using methods that include 2D digital image correlation (DIC). The main preliminary results are presented in this paper. Its performance has opened up important perspectives on the possibilities of detecting cracks, temperature variation and the presence of water in concrete structures.

KEYWORDS

structural health monitoring; optical fiber sensors; crack detection; digital image correlation

INTRODUCTION

Concrete structures are widely used in construction due to their durability and strength. However, one common issue that can arise in these structures is the development of damages due to many causes such as accidents and environmental impacts. Damages in concrete structures are often characterized by the presence of cracks which can have major impact on the structural integrity. Cracks can compromise the overall strength of the structure and reduce its load-carrying capacity but also increase the potential for moisture and chemical ingress.

To assess the risk associated with fissures in concrete structures, a crack width threshold is often used as a diagnostic criterion. This threshold serves as an indication of the severity of the crack and helps determine the appropriate course of action. The crack width threshold varies depending on the type of structure and its intended use. In general, a crack width threshold of around 0.2 millimeters is considered acceptable for most structures according to Eurocode 2. Cracks below this threshold are typically categorized as hairline cracks and are considered to have minimal impact on the structure's performance and durability. However, cracks wider than the threshold can indicate more significant issues and require closer inspection.

Regular inspections and monitoring of crack widths are essential to detect changes and evaluate the progression of fissures over time. Therefore, within this framework, the SENTMI project (PSPC Region 2020) seeks to make advancements in monitoring techniques and devices, particularly focusing on a recent and highly promising solution: optical fiber sensors. The collaborative venture involves the participation of Léon Grosse, Inouid, and Brochier Technologies, as well as the research laboratory LOCIE from Université Savoie Mont-Blanc. This consortium brings together specialized knowledge in sensor development, optical fiber innovation, and civil engineering construction. The LOCIE laboratory specifically contributes expertise in the fields of structural and energetic diagnostics for buildings.

This work aims to assess the SENTMI textile sensor capability of detecting and measuring cracks in concrete structures, as well as its capability of sensing water presence and temperature variation.

METHODS AND EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS

Brochier technologies, known for their expertise in optical fiber weaving, has developed a variety of patches with different configurations that consider parameters such as fiber diameter, density, and length (Brochier et al. 2017). These patches can be either embedded within concrete samples or adhered to their surface. They are then connected at two ends to a light source and a detector. The detector, developed by Inouid, provides data of light intensity and it has a wireless communication with computers via an application, also developed by Inouid. This technique allows the management of parameters for data acquisition and exporting, as well as setting threshold to trigger an alarming system. The sensor technology cannot be further explained as patents are pending and confidentiality is requested by the consortium during the life of the project (2020-2024).

Concrete samples were manufactured in the LOCIE laboratory using cement “performat CEM I 52,5N CE PM-CP2 NF” and prismatic steel formworks of sizes 40 cm x 10 cm x 10 cm and 60 cm x 15 cm x 15 cm in addition to a real scale beam of 330 cm x 24 cm x 14 cm (Figure 1). A mixture of sand (0-6 mm), gravel (4-10 mm for the smaller sample and 10 – 20 mm for the other two sizes), cement performat and water was used. The concrete is supposed to be classified by C30/37 following the Eurocode2 regulation. To facilitate the identification of crack propagation, a notch with a height of 2cm is created in the sample. This is achieved by placing a rectangular piece of wood at the midpoint of the sample's length prior to pouring the concrete. In order to induce crack formation, a maximum bending moment is applied, which is accomplished through three-point bending tests. The loading is specifically applied to the central region of the sample, adjacent to the upright section of the notch.

a) Sample sized 40 cm x 10 cm x 10 cm and 60 cm x 15 cm x 15 cm

b) Beam of 330 cm x 24 cm x 14 cm placed at the 3-point bending test machine

Figure 1. SENTMI different sample sizes

Damage and crack opening

To calibrate the measurement of cracks, initially the method consisted in using on-surfaces patches and submitting samples to a three-point bending test and comparing the crack width evolution obtained by 2D digital image correlation to the signal coming from the patch. By comparing these two types of data, a coefficient of linear correlation could be calculated.

To better understand the response of the patch to the displacement of its two edges, a new way of calibrating was implemented so the image correlation could be used as a way of verifying this calibration. It consists in testing the patch alone by gripping two edges of the patch in a compression/traction machine (Step 1 from figure 2), connecting it to the light source and detector (Step 2 from figure 2) and applying cycles of stretching and releasing at 0.5 mm/min (Step 3 from figure 2) to obtain the equation of correlation (Step 4 from figure 2). First cycles were done with a displacement of 2 mm (orange plot in figure 3 b). The patch responded in a consistent way by reducing the light

intensity when stretching and regaining it when coming back to the initial tension configuration. This response seemed to be linear, until another test that would apply 3 mm of displacement (blue plot in figure 3 b) from one edge to the other showed that the loosening of light intensity for 3 mm stretching (20cd) was not linearly proportional (150%) to the decrease of the patch signal in a 2 mm stretch (15cd), therefore, the response is not exactly linear.

Figure 2. Steps for calibrating the SENTMI sensor for measuring cracks.

a) SENTMI textile sensor being calibrated

b) Sensor's response to cycles of 2 mm and 3 mm extension and contraction

Figure 3. Calibration campaign of the SENTMI fibre optic textile sensor

Different cycles including a long stretch of 8mm were done to obtain the equation of correlation by polynomial regression. The post treatment of the patch signal includes considering the initial value of light intensity as the reference (zero) so we can work only with the increments. The coefficient of correlation that will multiply the light intensity increment correspond to the sensor resolution. It means that, a coefficient of 0.05 will be used if every 0.05 mm of stretch results in the variation of 1 unit of light intensity. Therefore, this coefficient can be described as:

$$K = \frac{\partial d}{\partial I} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Where K is the coefficient of correlation, d is the displacement of one edge of the patch with respect to the other edge and I is the light intensity.

Six samples were used in this campaign of crack monitoring, two of each mentioned sample size. After being calibrated, the patches were glued to the surfaces of the samples and subjected to a three-point bending test, similar to the approach employed by Gkantou et al. (2019) and Cimellaro et al. (2019) in their investigation of crack detection in reinforced concrete structures. The smaller samples were positioned symmetrically between two parallel supports and bent using a compression displacement-driven method, with a rate of 0.5mm/min. On the other hand, the beams underwent a force-driven three-point bending test, with a rate of 0.05 KN/s. To ensure accurate calibration, a 2D image correlation technique was employed, utilizing a NIKON D7000 camera with a 60 mm focal length. This enabled the monitoring of crack evolution during the three-point bending test by establishing a reference distance.

In accordance with the recommendations outlined in the DIC Good Practices Guide from the International Digital Image Correlation Society (2017), a 2D-DIC approach was adopted for this study. The sample is assumed to possess and maintain planar characteristics throughout the test, while also maintaining a consistent stand-off distance. To create a suitable speckle pattern for analysis, a white background color was applied across the region of interest (ROI). Subsequently, black-colored circular speckles were randomly placed on the white background to provide contrast.

The frame rate employed should align with the anticipated rate of variation of the quantity of interest (QOI) to ensure accurate results. If the displacement between frames is too large, DIC algorithms may struggle to locate the subset position in the resulting images (International Digital Image Correlation Society, 2018). For this particular study, a frame rate of 5 seconds was chosen, accompanied by an exposure time of 1/500 seconds. The captured images are of size 4928 x 3264 pixels and possess a resolution of 300 x 300 dpi. These images were processed using GOM Correlate 2018 software, which facilitated the exportation of point-to-point distances in xlsx file format.

a) Small concrete sample b) Reinforced concrete beam
 Figure 4. 2D Digital Image Correlation (DIC) performed at GOM Correlate 2018 Software.

Sensitivity to water detection

The SENTMI sensor is sensitive to the presence of water. Due to its reliance on the optical phenomenon of ray propagation and its ability to account for the surrounding environment, it reacts to changes in the medium caused by the different directions of light propagation in water and air.

Within this method, three samples with embedded patches and 6 samples featuring on-surface patches were used. The samples are placed within a prismatic box, and during the test, the water level systematically rises and falls (range of interest between points A and B from figure 5). Meanwhile, the detector captures the signal from the patch, allowing for a comparison between the water level and the acquired signal. When the sensor is measured in a dry condition and then exposed to a rising water level, it responds by decreasing the intensity of light, indicating that fewer rays are reaching the detector.

Figure 5. Scheme of the test for water detection. A and B represent the moment when the water first interact with the patch and the moment when the patch is totally submerged.

Sensitivity to temperature detection

In the experimental campaign focused on monitoring temperature fluctuations in concrete structures, three samples containing embedded patches were tested. The patch was exposed to a temperature gradient applied to the concrete sample. The embedded patch was positioned perpendicular to the horizontal plane, thereby aligning it perpendicularly to the temperature gradient. The optical fibers within the patch were oriented vertically, positioned 2 cm away from the sample's surface where an infrared lamp was directed. The lamp heated one side of the sample, while the access connectors of the patch were located on the top surface (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Setup for testing the SENTMI patch's response to temperature variation

The temperature was measured using a FLIR Systems AB thermal camera, specifically the E60bx 1.0 model (Figure 6 b). It is worth mentioning that the camera captures the temperature at the surface of the sample. Hence, the distance between the patch and the specific spot being measured on the external surface of the concrete structure should be considered.

RESULTS

Damage and crack opening

The measurements of light signal over time obtained by the patch, as well as the measurements of crack width done via digital image correlation were treated using python, where the equation of correlation can be applied.

The improvement of patch configurations by Brochier Technologies, optimized by the testing on LOCIE concrete structures at Savoie Mont Blanc University, has led to significant advancements in the resolution of the SENTMI sensor. The configurations have been refined, resulting in the achievement

of a sensor resolution that can reach 0.01 mm. In this context, sensor resolution refers to the minimum increment in crack width required to produce a unit change in light intensity.

Figure 7. Main results of the SENTMI sensor for crack measurement.

Figure 7 compares the evolution of real crack width, measured using Digital Image Correlation (red curve), with the signal obtained from the post-treated SENTMI patch (blue curve). The measurements were taken on samples of different sizes: 10 cm x 10 cm x 40 cm (a and b from Figure 7), 15 cm x 15 cm x 60 cm (c and d from Figure 7), and 14 cm x 24 cm x 330 cm (e and f from Figure 7).

By observing the curves, it is evident that the SENTMI patch signal closely follows the initiation and progression of the crack. The curves exhibit a high degree of overlap, indicating a strong correlation. The crack width curve shows an initial rapid increase as the crack first appears, followed by a slower and relatively consistent evolution. However, occasional abrupt increases occur due to material heterogeneity, such as the rupture of aggregates, causing non-linearities.

The behaviour of the crack differs among the three sample sizes. The 330 cm long beam had pre-existing cracks, allowing the patch to be placed directly on the main crack. As a result, the discontinuity (the nearly vertical part of the curve at the beginning) representing the moment of crack initiation is not observed, as seen in the smaller samples. Comparing the two smaller samples, it is noticeable that the initial crack width is different. The 15 cm x 15 cm x 60 cm samples tend to have larger initial cracks compared to the 10 cm x 10 cm x 40 cm samples, attributed to variations in aggregate size and size effects.

It is intriguing to observe how the SENTMI patch effectively tracks both the smooth evolution and sudden jumps in crack width. The patch demonstrates its capability to capture these changes accurately, providing valuable insights into crack behaviour.

The pre-calibration has shown to be effective for the smaller samples. In the graphics of a, b, c and d from figure 7, the equation of correlation is applied and the measurements acquired from the image correlation are plotted to verify if the equation of calibration managed to translate the light intensity data into displacement data. For the tests on the beam, however, the equation of calibration did not give a good result, as the graphics of e and f from figure 7 are post corrected by using the DIC curve to calibrate instead of verifying only. Few hypotheses are considered to account for the correlation equation's lack of precision for the reinforced concrete beams at the moment, the main one attributes it to the gluing technique. The gluing technique is an important concern, as we need to provide a sensor that can be easily installed by a non-specialist. However, so far it can still introduce inaccuracies, because of a lack of standardization regarding the glued surface area and the pre-tension applied to the patch, which is a flexible textile.

Sensitivity to water detection

The collected signals from the patch are correlated with the water level variation between the bottom and top of the patch. Since the patches used have a height of 5cm, the black curve in Figure 8, 9 and 10 represents the water level at the embedded or glued patch location on the sample. In the case of samples with embedded patches, crack formation was induced prior to the tests to facilitate water infiltration. Points A and B correspond to the instances when the water initially interacts with the patch and when the patch is completely submerged, respectively.

Figure 8. Reaction of patches glued on the samples' surface in function of the water level with three different ranges of light signal. Fibers positioned vertically.

When the water level rises and reaches the bottom of the patch (point A), the sensor reacts by reducing its light intensity. This response is consistent for both embedded and on-surface patches. However, they exhibit different behaviors during the second phase of the test, which involves the lowering of the water level. In the case of on-surface patches (Figure 8), their light signal begins to increase once again as the

water level falls below the bottom of the patch (point A), while the water is being drained from the container. On the contrary, embedded patches (Figure 9) continue to decrease their signal, gradually reaching a stable state. This indicates that embedded patches remain sensitive to the residual water present in the concrete.

Figure 9. Reaction of embedded patches in function of the water level, with three different ranges of light signal. Fibers positioned vertically.

The orientation of the fibers also has an important effect on the behaviour of the patch. When the fibers are placed vertically, the water level will vary with respect to the length of the fibers equally. The response to the medium is more intense at the fibers end, and therefore we see a strong decline of signal, in figure 8, as soon as the water enters in contact with the fibers. When the fibers are placed horizontally, the water level will cover an entire fiber one by one, and it will cause a response more proportional to the water level with respect to the patch height (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Reaction of patches glued on the samples' surface in function of the water level with three different ranges of light signal. Fibers positioned horizontally.

Sensitivity to temperature detection

Precise correlation between temperature and light intensity in response to concrete's temperature variations has not been achieved yet, as the sensor responses tend to be unique for each test. However, it is important to note that the sensor does exhibit a response to heating, which should be taken into consideration as it can introduce noise into the crack measurements.

During the heating process, the patch's signal is recorded and stored for a duration of 15 minutes while an infrared lamp heats one side of the concrete sample. The embedded patches in the tested samples

have demonstrated sensitivity to temperature variations and have shown a decrease in light signal ranging from 3% to 24% when subjected to temperature gradients ranging from 7 °C to 11 °C on the surface of the sample. Figure 11 illustrates the results from three patches, which have been plotted separately to highlight their signal variations. It should be noted that the varying levels of light intensity from one test to the other are a result of differences of the patches' configurations, including differences in fiber diameter and the number of fibers per centimeter within each patch.

Figure 11. Response of SENTMI patches to the applied temperature gradient, with three different ranges of light signal.

CONCLUSION AND PERSPECTIVES

This paper has presented the primary initial findings of a novel fiber optic-based sensor designed for structural health monitoring. The sensor aims to detect the presence of water, measure temperature variations, and quantify crack width within structures. The sensor utilizes a 2D patch containing woven optical fibers and is applied to concrete structures at the laboratory level. Various methods have been proposed to study the patch's response to different phenomena. The preliminary results are encouraging, and ongoing tests are being conducted in parallel with measurements in real constructions at sites from Leon Grosse projects.

It has been demonstrated that the optical fiber based textile sensor is capable of tracking the initiation and progression of cracks in concrete, the best results achieving a sensor resolution of 0.01 mm. The sensor's response to an increase in water level exhibited a remarkable sensitivity to water presence, as evidenced by a signal decrease ranging from 20% to 50% for the embedded patches when the dry concrete becomes saturated. Furthermore, the patch demonstrated sensitivity to temperature changes, as indicated by a signal decrease of 3% to 24% after the sample's temperature increased by 7°C to 11°C.

A direct correlation between temperature of the concrete structure and the light signal from the sensor inserted in this structure is yet to be found. The sensibility to this temperature fluctuation is being taken into consideration because although the tests for crack opening at the laboratory level can be done in a controlled environment, a fixed temperature cannot be guaranteed in real constructions. The tests performed at the University Savoie Mont Blanc on 1:1 scale structures (330 cm x 24 cm x 14 cm beams) have the assistance of a weather station so the daily temperature fluctuations can be monitored and used as a comparative factor between beams that are stored at the interior and the ones that are stored outdoors.

The distinction between the responses of embedded patches and on-surface patches in detecting water presence suggests that on-surface patches primarily react to the medium outside the sample within the box. This is evident from the rapid increase in signal when the water exits the box. On the other hand, the response of embedded patches appears to be more closely linked to the moisture content of the sample's material. The signal tends to remain relatively stable while the interior of the sample is still wet, indicating a correlation with the degree of saturation. This result is very important for fighting problems related to reinforcement corrosion, which is ranked among the top concerns in terms of structural problems, highlighting its widespread occurrence and the extensive financial implications for maintenance and repair.

The method of pre-calibration of the sensor has shown to be effective on the small samples' tests, providing the equation that describes the light intensity response to the extension and contraction of the sensor's tissue. In the tests on the beams, however, the equation of calibration could not accurately fit the light signal curve into the crack width curve and required a post correction. More tests of calibration are needed to account for different displacement rates in the three-point bending tests and differences between displacement-driven and force-driven approaches.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This study has been made possible through the financial support from La Région AURA (PSPC 2020), as well as the unwavering dedication and collaborative efforts of the participating entities including Leon Grosse, Inouid, Brochier Technologies, and the laboratory LOCIE from the University "Savoie Mont Blanc." These organizations have invested their financial and intellectual resources towards the development of a valuable tool in the construction industry, aiming to establish a safer and more efficient monitoring system.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

All necessary data is presented in this paper.

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